

METHODOLOGY OF FORMATION OF CONDITIONED REFLEX "AGENDA" IN PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8039310>

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Abstract.

In this article, the routine, which is a component of a healthy lifestyle, and its important components (normal physiological sleep, proper nutrition, physical activity, walking in the open air, proper organization of work activities) and the development of a dynamic stereotype of an orderly life in children from a young age and their own it is highlighted that teaching to acquire knowledge in time is one of the important tasks. At the same time, in order to determine the level of adherence to the agenda, the results of the first and second questionnaires were statistically analyzed, information was provided about the methods of forming the agenda among elementary school students and the effect of a correctly structured agenda on the physical and mental development of the student body, and the positive impact on mastering the subjects taught at school.

Key words.

routine, reflex, intellectual, dynamic stereotype, nervous system, sleep, cerebral cortex, higher nervous activity, organism, physiology, biological rhythm, cell, stress, hormone, mental performance, hygiene, mood.

INTRODUCTION

Comprehensive reforms implemented in the education system in our republic are aimed at ensuring the high quality of education, and one of the main factors determining success in this direction is the acquisition of modern knowledge, skills and qualifications of pedagogues, as well as scientific research of innovative informational didactic forms of education.

This, in turn, requires a fundamental reform of the education system, because an excellent education system plays a decisive role in educating students-youth, who determine the future intellectual opportunities and development of our republic, to be creative and independent in all aspects. If the school curriculum does not properly plan to accelerate the mental activity of students, it will be difficult to achieve high educational efficiency and mastery rate [5].

It is one of the highest tasks of every pedagogue to carry out education and upbringing at the same time, to raise physically healthy, mentally developed, bright-minded young people. Young people are the future of our country, their healthy growth and development in the future. Most of the current reforms are aimed at young people. In raising young people to become mature and intellectual individuals, forming the conditioned reflex of "agenda" in them from a young age takes a key place in achieving the goal.

A healthy lifestyle is a social phenomenon that ensures the achievement of a high level of health, based on the acquisition of skills that serve to ensure the safety of a person's life and health [5,20]. The main component of a healthy lifestyle is the daily routine.

Agenda is understood as regulation of human activities, efficient use of time, making a plan for the day and adapting to this plan. As a result of forming a routine in the child, a conditional reflex chain is formed in the nervous system, the type of activity during the day adapts to a certain routine [20]. Naturally, the daily schedule cannot be the same for everyone and it is made according to the child's age, health, work ability and household conditions. A person's healthy and unhealthy lifestyle also depends on the correct and incorrect organization of the daily routine [21].

I. P. Pavlov's teaching about the coordination and control function of the higher nervous system and the central nervous system is the basis for creating a daily schedule that includes work and rest, as well as the sequence of different types of training [14,16].

When children's daily routine is organized correctly, the child does not get tired, always performs the same activity at the same time, and dynamic stereotypes are formed in the nervous system, students grow up disciplined and educated [14].

Several physiological conditions are taken into account when planning the daily routine of elementary school pupils.

First, the specific features of higher nervous activity are considered. At this age, the cells of the cerebral cortex have the property of being easily dislodged. They are characterized by rapid and relatively unstable formation of the reflex.

Secondly, it is based on the functional biological rhythm of the nervous system.

Pupils' intellectual ability, i.e. cerebral hemispheres, have high indicators in the morning and afternoon hours, and its decrease corresponds to the evening hours. During the observations, it was observed that the mental performance of

schoolchildren changed, i.e. it increased 2 times during the day (the first from 800 to 1200, the second from 1600 to 1800).

The first increase in mental performance is higher and longer than the second [5,14,16]. Therefore, knowing the peak times of mental work activity in the preparation of students' training load and making it based on this helps to prevent various cases of mental exhaustion.

The state of change of mental performance indicators of schoolchildren, not all children have a high biorhythmic state in this interval. For example, special application of periodic changes of physiological functions of children of junior school age allows to divide them into biorhythm groups of different nature. They are divided into the following groups:

- the first group consists of children whose physiological indicators double during the day;
- the second group consists of children whose functional indicators increase by the same amount in the middle of the day;
- the third group consists of children with high functional indicators;
- the fourth group consists of children who do not have a high index [5,14].

Timely and correct implementation of important components of the daily routine (proper nutrition, normal physiological sleep, outdoor walks, physical activity (morning physical education), proper organization of labor activities) has a positive effect on the child's health and healthy intellectual development (Fig. 1)

Figure 2. Important components of the order of the day

All types of activities are carried out sequentially in the daily routine of elementary school students, positively affects the process of education and upbringing of students, helps to form an educated, responsible, healthy person.

To date, a number of scientific studies have been conducted on the formation of a healthy lifestyle in students. But due to the lack of scientific information

regarding the formation of the agenda, it is necessary to carry out scientific research works in this direction.

The formation of students' agenda and the ability to adhere to it is a multi-faceted process, which cannot be achieved by the activities of a single researcher, and for this, the use of school teachers, parents, and active students will be effective.

The formation of the students' agenda is carried out by the following formula:

Teacher + family (parents) + pupil - pupil = Order of the day

(formula for forming an agenda in students)

It is important for the teacher to work together with parents and active students in forming the students' agenda. It is important for the teacher to carry out the following tasks in forming the students' agenda:

- firstly, the study of the child's family situation and based on this

- formation of the student's agenda;

- secondly, to parents the Order of the day from the child's youth explain the important aspects of its formation and implementation;

- thirdly, important components of the agenda to parents provide complete information about;

- fourthly, for parents to form a routine for children to explain the positive impact on the educational process and mental development;

- fifth, to explain the impact on children's health.

Therefore, methods requiring complex work were included in the methodology of agenda formation.

The purpose of the study: to form a daily routine, which is an important component of a healthy lifestyle, in primary school students.

Research object and methods.

Research object. As an object of scientific research, a total of 933 elementary schools of 6, 28 general education schools in Qibray district of Tashkent region of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 10 general education school in Fergana city of Fergana region, 40 general education schools in Fergana district, 4.55 - general education schools in Kumgorgan district of Surkhandarya region students were taken.

RESEARCH METHODS.

In the process of research, studying and analyzing the scientific and methodological research works of scientists of various fields, conducting and analyzing questionnaires, pedagogical observation, developing handouts, developing methodological recommendations for students, teachers, parents,

information communication technology (animation , videos), mathematical-statistical analysis and generalization of experiment-test results were used.

The obtained results and their analysis.

In the course of the research, a questionnaire was taken from the elementary school students, and based on the interview, it was determined to what extent they had an understanding of the agenda and its importance. This survey will serve as a basis for further research (tables 1-3).

Table 1

Level of adherence to the order of the day of elementary school pupils of 28-6 general education schools of Qibray district

School	Class	Pupils amount		Amount of pupils following the agenda		Amount of pupils following the agenda		The number of pupils who do not follow the agenda	
		total	girls	total	girls	total	girls	total	girls
28	1 "A"	32	16	10	6	5	3	17	7
	2 "A"	34	15	8	5	5	3	21	7
	2 "B"	9	4	2	1	2	2	5	1
	3 "A"	30	17	7	4	5	3	18	10
	3 "B"	11	3	3	2	1	0	7	1
	4 "A"	34	21	6	4	7	4	21	13
6	1 "B"	19	6	9	2	2	1	8	3
	2 "A"	28	15	8	5	7	3	13	7
	2 "B"	22	14	8	5	6	3	8	6
	3 "A"	23	16	7	3	8	5	8	8
	3 "B"	23	15	6	3	8	4	9	8
	4 "A"	28	14	10	4	6	2	12	8
	4 "B"	23	16	7	4	4	3	12	9
	жами	316	172	91	48	66	36	159	88

2- Table

Level of adherence to the order of the day of elementary school pupils of the 10th general education school in the city of Fergana, Fergana region, and the 40th general education school in the Fergana district

School	Class	Pupils amount		Amount of pupils following the agenda		Amount of pupils following the agenda		The number of pupils who do not follow the agenda	
		total	girls	total	girls	total	girls	total	girls

10	1 "A"	33	18	3	2	10	6	20	10
	1 "Г"	31	16	2	1	8	4	21	11
	2 "B"	25	12	1	1	10	5	14	6
	2 "B"	26	21	0	0	12	6	14	15
	3 "A"	41	27	6	3	13	6	22	18
	3 " B"	42	23	5	2	12	4	25	17
	4 "A"	36	20	6	3	7	4	23	13
	4 "B"	42	18	7	4	10	5	25	9
40	1 "A"	31	10	0	0	6	3	25	7
	2 "A"	36	18	2	1	6	3	28	14
	3 "A"	23	9	3	1	7	4	13	4
	4 "A"	27	13	2	2	5	3	20	8
	General	393	205	37	20	106	53	250	132

3- Table

Level of adherence to the order of the day of elementary school students of the 4 th general education school and the 55th general education school in the Kumkorgan district of the Surkhandarya region

School	Class	Pupils amount		Amount of pupils following the agenda		Amount of pupils following the agenda		The number of pupils who do not follow the agenda	
		total	girls	total	girls	total	girls	total	girls
4	1 "B"	25	9	0	0	9	4	16	5
	2 "A"	26	14	2	1	8	5	16	8
	3 "A"	26	8	3	1	6	4	17	3
	3 " B"	25	10	2	2	6	3	17	5
	4 "B"	30	16	4	2	9	4	17	10
55	1 "A"	28	13	0	0	7	5	21	8
	2 "A"	19	9	3	2	5	2	11	5
	3 "A"	26	12	3	1	4	3	19	8
	4" B"	19	9	2	2	6	4	11	3
Total		224	100	19	11	60	34	145	55

According to the results of the analysis, 91 (28.8%) of the 316 elementary school students of the 6th and 28th general secondary schools of the Tashkent region follow the agenda (48 girls), 66 (20.9%) partially follow it (36 girls), 159 (50.3%) did not follow the agenda at all (88 girls). 37 out of 393 students (9.4%) of primary school students of the 10th general education school and 40th general

school of Fergana region follow the agenda (20 girls), 106 (27%) partially follow the agenda (53 250 (63.6%) do not follow the agenda at all (132 girls).

Out of a total of 224 elementary school students of Surkhandarya region 4-55, 19 (8.5%) follow the agenda (11 girls), 60 (26.8%) partially follow it (55 girls), 145 it was found that 64.7% of them do not follow the agenda at all (55 girls).

This means that the important components of students' routines are morning physical education, hygienically full sleep, physical activity and educational activities are not performed on time. This has a negative effect on the growing body, causes a violation of physiological processes in the body, the child lags behind in growth and development, besides, the mental capacity also decreases, and the rate of mastering subjects deteriorates.

In order to form an agenda for schoolchildren, the following activities were carried out: Roundtable discussions were organized with class leaders and parents about the positive impact of the order of the day, which is an important component of a healthy lifestyle, on the educational process and health; Development and implementation of a recommendation (for teachers and parents) on the organization of the agenda for primary school pupils; "My order of the day!" for elementary school pupils (grades 1-4) development and implementation of the recommendation;

- Development and implementation of handout "My agenda" for primary school students;
- Development and implementation of an infographic animated 2D video called "My order of the day" using information and communication technologies to organize the agenda of elementary school students;

If demonstrative, animated, explanatory, and motivational methods are used in the formation of the order of the day for elementary school students, explanatory work is carried out in cooperation with parents, dynamic stereotypes about the agenda are formed in them, that is, a conditioned reflex of the agenda is formed in the child.

The result of the survey conducted in order to determine the effectiveness of the research work on the formation of the agenda for elementary school students is as follows.

Table 4

Province	School e	The first questionnaire is the result of the survey		
		Amount of pupils	Amount of students following the agenda	The number of students who do not follow the agenda

		Total	Total	%	Total	%
Tashkent region	28	150	36	24%	114	76%
	6	166	55	33,1%	111	66,8%
Total		316	91	28,7%	225	71,2%
Fergana region	10	276	30	10,8%	246	89,1%
	40	117	7	5,9%	110	94%
Total		393	37	9,4%	356	90,5%
Surkhandarya region	4	132	11	8,3%	121	28,7%
	55	92	8	8,7%	84	23,9%
Total		224	19	8,5%	205	26,7%
General indicator		933	147	15,7%	786	84,3%

Table 5

Province	School e	The second questionnaire is the result of the survey				
		Agenda for pupils	Amount of students following the agenda		The number of students who do not follow the agenda	
			Total	Total	Per cent (%)	Total
Tashkent region	28	150	91	60,6	59	39,3
	6	166	83	50	83	69,8
Total		316	174	43,3	142	44,9
Fergana region	10	276	85	30,7	191	69,2
	40	117	48	41	69	58,9
Total		393	133	33,8	260	66,1
Surkhandarya region	4	132	59	44,6	73	55,3
	55	92	42	45,6	50	54,3
Total		224	101	45	123	54,9
General indicator		933	408	43,8	525	56,2

CONCLUSION

A total of 933 elementary (1st-4th grade) students of Tashkent region, Fergana region, Surkhandarya region took part in the second survey, which was conducted

to determine the effectiveness of the scientific research on the formation of students' agenda.

It was found that 174 students of the elementary schools of the 28-6 general education schools in Tashkent region had an agenda, which was 43.3 percent (%), and it was found that 133 students of the 10-40 general education schools in the Fergana region had an agenda, which was 33.8 percent (%) it was found that 101 students of 4-55 secondary schools in Surkhondarya region had formed an agenda, which was 45 percent (%). 408 out of 933 elementary school students of the schools where the experiment was carried out had an agenda, which is 43.8 percent. The difference between the first and second questionnaires was 28.1 percent.

The fact that the rest of the students participating in the survey do not follow the agenda partially or at all, requires serious work in this direction.

In order to do this, it is important for the primary education of higher education institutions to provide students with an additional lesson, a training course on the main component of a healthy lifestyle, the agenda and its components, the methods of agenda formation, the importance of children's lives, and to fill the existing gap in students. is enough.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The structure of the daily routine of students of junior school age, taking into account the specific characteristics of their higher nervous activity, helps the healthy development of the growing organism. At this age, the cells of the cerebral cortex have the property of being easily dislodged. They are characterized by rapid and relatively unstable formation of the reflex.

Important components of the daily routine regimen (proper nutrition, normal physiological sleep, walking in the air, physical activity (morning physical activity), with timely proper organization of labor activities) has a positive effect on the child's health and healthy intellectual development.

To do this, inform students about the agenda, explain the importance of the agenda, distribute handouts with the agenda in the form of a table called "My Agenda", prepare and show animations and videos in the form of cartoons, develop methodical recommendations for parents. and a positive result is achieved through distribution.

Forming a routine for students based on hygienic requirements:

- to the proper growth of the child's organism;
- strong immunity;
- mentally and physically healthy development;
- to master school subjects well,

- to be orderly and disciplined;
- efficient use of time;
- teaches to be an excellent student.

So, the "agenda" is mandatory for elementary school students forming a reflex helps to form a healthy, well-rounded person.

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